

WORK AND STUDY OF ALEKSANDR FAYNBERG

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ABSTRACT

Aleksandr Faynberg is considered to be one of the most acclaimed poets in Uzbekistan. Although his nationality belongs to other nation, he left invaluable piece of his writings about Uzbek culture, customs and life. His all poems were written with all his heart dedicating his life to the advancement of Uzbek poetry. Poet's early life, achievements and his contributions to our national literature would be further discussed.

Key words: *Journalism, poetry, philosophy, cultural diversity, inspiring ideas, creativity.*

Introduction

Aleksandr Faynberg was born in Tashkent in the years of world war two. His parents were originally from Russia and settled in this city long before poet came to life. In his books, Faynberg describes Tashkent as a city of magic, its traditions and how people friendly in here. Also he describes the beauty and charm of the city, depicting the nature of Uzbekistan, and pointing out these outstanding scenes were triggers in his writing journey. He shades light the relationship he enjoyed most in here, how people in Tashkent helped him when he lost his parents. He was not taken to care houses or abandoned on his own, but he was raised the same way as most children

were brought up that times. He was grateful for Uzbek people for being so warm to him and put all of his strength to make nationwide the culture of Uzbekistan.

Methods

Faynberg graduated Tashkent State University and for some time he worked as a part of a team in Writer's Union. He was author of more than 15 books, according to his screenplay writing abilities, many films were shot back that times. His poems were published in internationally recognized journals called "The Youths ", "Star of Asia " and " New world ".

In late nineties, there was catastrophic airplane damage when Uzbek team Pakhtakor was arriving to Tashkent , according to his writings expressing empathy for those in this plane crash a film was made named " Their stadium is on the sky" outlining how big loose it was for our nation.

For some years, he arranged meeting training seminars for young writers which paved his way to climb career ladder. In 2004 year. he was nominated with Pushkin medal as he was one of those writers who were enriching cultural diversity of our literature coming up with new ideas to address various existing issues in our society. [1]. He wrote a descriptive poem named "String of the Rubaiyat" where he best creates best image of Uzbek chayhana which puts a smile to the face of readers.

He has published following books " Cycling treks" (1965), " Etude"(1967), " Poems" (1977), Distant Bridges" (1978), "The Seal of the Sky" (1982), "Short Wave" (1983), "Net" (1986), "Free Sonnets" (1990), "Don't Cry, Darling" (1997), "Mine" (2000), "Free Sonnets" (2003), "Leaf" (2008).

He translated Navoiy's scripts to Russian to promote Uzbek literature and to reach more audiences. Even the most acknowledged Uzbek writer A. Oripov praised his poetic skills as he was impressed how a Russian poet could carry on his all studies in Uzbek literature dedicating his whole life to serve to his country.

Results

Родина

Меж знойными квадратами полей
она легла до горного отрога —
гудроновая старая дорога
в тени пирамидальных тополей.
Я в юности не раз ходил по ней
с теодолитом и кривой треногой.
Я пил айран в той мазанке убогой,
где и теперь ни окон, ни дверей.
Печальный край. Но именно отсюда
я родом был, я родом есть и буду.
Ау, Европа! Я не знаю Вас.
Вдали орла безмолвное круженье.
В зубах травинка. Соль у самых глаз.
И горестно, и счастливо мгновенье.
Motherland
Between the sultry squares of fields
she lay down to the mountain spur -
old tar roady
in the shade of pyramidal poplars.
I walked along it more than once in my youth
with theodolite and crooked tripod.
I drank ayran in that wretched hut,
where now there are no windows or doors.
A sad land. But it's from here
I was born, I am born and will be.
Hey, Europe! I don't know you.

In the distance the eagle silently circles.
A blade of grass in your teeth. Sadness right in the eyes.
Both sad and happy moments.

In this poem , it can be seen how Faynberg sophisticatedly showed the true picture of Uzbek culture. First landscapes , roads nature were described, then Uzbek national drink ayran was also mentioned. He referred to to Europe as he is not interested in anything offered by it, as he again proved his loyalty and conveyed the painful problems of that times Uzbek were going through. It was a wartime, millions of uzbeks lost their flesh and bone in the battle becoming its victim, sadness in the eyes is the metaphor used to express hard times of grief and remembering sweet and bitter memories of the past.

Conclusion

Uzbek poet Faynberk left his treasures in Uzbek literature being the first one to promote and sing about Uzbek society. In his writings we can see the pain , the chill, the happiness, the tragedy of nation that times as he directly wrote what was in his heart and skillfully placed all the words to the paper.

Reference:

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